

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The relationship of the quality of health services assurance dimensions with patient satisfaction in health services in Lepo-Lepo Health Centers Kendari City, Indonesia

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Abstract

Background: Currently, Public Health Center are faced with progress in human civilization which demands fast, quality and satisfying health services for customers. To deal with these demands, the Public Health Center should carry out service management engineering following developments in the community.

Objective: The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between the quality of health services on the assurance dimension and patient satisfaction at the Lepo-Lepo Public Health Center, Kendari City in 2021.

Methods: The type of research used was an analytical survey research with a Cross Sectional Study approach. The study population was 448 patients. The research sample taken was 211 patients. Collecting data by using a questionnaire. Data analysis was performed by Univariate and Bivariate.

Results: The results showed that there was a relationship between assurance and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City, with a value of $p=0.042$ ($p>0.05$).

Conclusion: There is a relationship between assurance and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City.

Keywords: Health Center; Quality; Assurance; Satisfaction

1. Introduction

Satisfaction is an expression of people's feelings that arise after comparing perceptions of the performance of a product. According to [1] states that the quality of health services is the degree to which the needs of the community or individuals are met for health care in accordance with good professional standards by using resources fairly, efficiently, effectively within limitations safely and satisfying customers in accordance with good norms and ethics. According to [2] suggests that the concept of service quality related to patient satisfaction is determined by five elements commonly known as service quality "SERVQUAL" (reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangible). The quality of health services shows the level of perfection of health services in creating a sense of satisfaction in each patient. The more perfect the satisfaction, the better the quality of health services.

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In regulating health problems, it is necessary to have a special institution that is responsible for administering health insurance, where the institution must provide good service quality in order to achieve service satisfaction. The quality of health services shows the level of perfection of health services in creating a sense of satisfaction for each patient. The more perfect the satisfaction, the better the quality of health services [3]. The quality of health services can be meant solely from the medical technical aspect which is only directly related to medical services and patients, or the quality of health from a social point of view and the health care system as a whole, including the consequences of administrative, financial, equipment and manpower management. Other health [4].

Health service is one of the efforts held jointly in a health organization to maintain and improve health, prevent, cure disease and restore the health of individuals, families, groups or communities. The quality of health services needs to be improved because of the community's or individual's needs for health that are in accordance with standards with reasonable, efficient, effective use of resources within the limited capacity of the Government and the community, and are carried out safely and satisfactorily in accordance with good norms and ethics so that people feel satisfied. With the services provided. The creation of service quality will certainly create satisfaction for service users. The quality of this service can ultimately provide several benefits, including the establishment of a harmonious relationship between providers of goods and services and customers, providing a good basis for creating customer loyalty and forming a word of mouth recommendation that is profitable for service providers [5].

Health services are one of the sub-systems of national health services. Based on Minister of Health regulations number 75 of 2014 that must be carried out by Public Health Center is a service that is based on a national commitment to improve integrated public health status. Patient satisfaction is one of the important indicators in improving health services, because patients as bio-psychosocial beings require the fulfillment of expectations from health aspects (biological), satisfaction aspects (psychological), and cultural aspects. However, in the national health insurance era, the quality of health services provided declined. This is caused by the lack of information provided by officers to the community, because it will affect the perception of patients who want to go to the Public Health Center [8].

Users of health services at the Public Health Center demand quality services not only regarding healing from physical illness but also regarding satisfaction with the attitudes, knowledge and skills of officers in providing services and the availability of adequate facilities and infrastructure that can provide comfort. With the increasing quality of service, the function of services at the Public Health Center needs to be improved to be more effective and efficient and provide satisfaction to patients and the community. The function of the Public Health Center which is very heavy in providing services to the community is faced with several challenges in terms of human resources and increasingly sophisticated health equipment, but must still provide the best service [9].

Good service quality can improve service quality and patient satisfaction. So that satisfied customers will share satisfaction with producers or service providers. Even satisfied customers will share their taste and experience with other customers [6]. Patients feel dissatisfied due to failure to communicate, time crisis, product or service quality, service quality or quality, price, and cost. One of the causes of patient dissatisfaction in health services is the quality of health services. Good service quality can improve service quality and patient satisfaction. So that satisfied customers will share satisfaction with producers or service providers [7].

The initial survey conducted by researchers at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center in Kendari City, on some patients using health services, it was found that some complained about services in the form of long service waiting times, limited seats, slow service officers, unresponsive attitude of officers and vehicle parking. Limited. Based on this information, researchers are interested in conducting research on health service satisfaction by patients at the Lepo-Lepo Public Health Center, Kendari City. The purpose of this study was to analyze the relationship between the assurance dimension and patient satisfaction at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center in Kendari City in 2021.

2. Material and methods

The type of research used is analytical survey research with a Cross Sectional Study approach. The study population was 448 patients. The research sample taken was 211 patients. Respondents' inclusion criteria were patients who visited at least 2 visits, resided in the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, and were willing to be respondents. Collecting data by using a questionnaire. Data analysis was performed by Univariate and Bivariate.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Univariate Analysis

3.1.1. Assurance

Assurance services provided must be free from various dangers and risks. Associated with knowledge, courtesy, and the ability of employees to foster customer trust and confidence [10]. The distribution of respondents according to assurance is presented in table 1;

Table 1 Distribution of respondents according to Assurance in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021

Number	Assurance	Amount (n)	Percentage (%)
1	enough	176	83
2	Not enough	35	17
Total		211	100

Source: Primary Data, year 2021

Table 1 shows that of the 211 respondents (100%), most of the respondents have sufficient assurance, namely 176 respondents (83.4%) compared to respondents who have low work motivation, namely 35 respondents (16.6%).

3.1.2. Service Quality

According to [2] suggests that the concept of service quality related to patient satisfaction is determined by five elements commonly known as service quality "SERVQUAL" (reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangible). The quality of health services shows the level of perfection of health services in creating a sense of satisfaction in each patient. The more perfect the satisfaction, the better the quality of health services. The distribution of respondents according to *Service Quality* is presented in table 2.

Table 2 Distribution of respondents according to Service Quality in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021

Number	Service Quality	Amount (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Satisfied	152	72
2	Not Satisfied	58	28
Total		211	100

Source: Primary Data, year 2021

Table 2 shows that of the 211 respondents (100%), most of the respondents have satisfied Service Quality, namely 152 respondents (72%) compared to respondents who have dissatisfied Service Quality, which is 58 respondents (28%).

3.1.3. Bivariate Analysis

The Relationship between Assurance and Patient Satisfaction in Lepo-Lepo Health Center Health Services in 2021

The relationship between assurance and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center in Kendari City can be presented in table 3.

Table 3 shows that of the 176 respondents (100%) who have sufficient assurance, there are more patients who say they are satisfied with the Service Quality, namely 131 respondents (74.4%) than patients who say they are not satisfied with the Service Quality, which are 45 respondents (25.6 %). Meanwhile, from 35 respondents (100%) who had less assurance, there were more patients who stated they were satisfied with Service Quality, namely 21 respondents (60%) than patients who stated they were not satisfied with Service Quality, namely 14 respondents (40%)

The results of the chi square test obtained a value of $p = 0.042$ ($p < 0.05$) meaning H_0 is rejected. This shows that there is a relationship between Assurance and Patient Satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021.

Table 3 Relationship between assurance and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021

Assurance	Service Quality				Amount (n)		P
	Satisfied		Satisfied		N	%	
	N	%	n	%			
enough	131	74	45	26	176	100	0.042
Not enough	21	60	14	40	35	100	
Total	152	72	59	28	211	100	

Source: Primary Data 2021

Along with the development of technology and information, the development of services in the health sector is also increasing rapidly. This development is also accompanied by a very high demand from the community for health services. Nursing as one of the health workers who provide services for 24 hours should improve to improve the quality of its services in order to provide quality services, conditions that occur in Indonesia are still many complain about the existence of nursing services that are less than optimal. Many patients complain that nurses are less friendly and slow in handling patient complaints. The high workload, the large number of delegated tasks from doctors and the large number of patients are often the reasons why services are less than optimal [11].

Basically there are 5 dimensions that can be assessed to determine customer satisfaction through the dimensions of the quality of nursing services, namely the dimension of form is a physical appearance in the form of facilities and infrastructure that exist in the services provided, including the appearance of nurses. The dimension of reliability is the ability of nurses to provide services in accordance with established service standards. While the responsiveness dimension is the willingness of nurses in providing services to convey information and help respond to patient needs immediately. The guarantee dimension means that the services provided are the best or competent, and can be trusted without any doubt. While the dimension of attention shows the degree of attention that nurses give to each patient seriously so that they can establish good communication relationships and are able to understand what the patient's needs are [1]

Based on the research findings in table 3, it shows that, in general, there are more patients who state sufficient assurance than patients who state less assurance. This shows that the higher the assurance, the higher the level of patient satisfaction with health services. On the other hand, the lower the assurance, the lower the level of patient satisfaction with the health services of the Lepo-Lepo Public Health Center. This happens because patients are increasingly aware of their needs and desires in health services, where they want knowledge of competent officers in their fields, politeness of officers in providing services, the ability of officers to grow trust and confidence in patients, quality and satisfying patients and optimal health services. Sustainable. Quality of service is an option that will affect the satisfaction of patients who will seek treatment at the Public Health Center.

The quality of service that will create its own satisfaction for its patients. The creation of quality services that can provide benefits to the Public Health Center and patients who will become harmonious. Global progress has a positive impact on the service industry, so service companies must pay attention to the quality of services or services they have provided to patients. Each institution has advantages and disadvantages both in terms of concepts, facilities and services to patients, this is a consideration for patients. As a health institution that has a mission to improve the degree of public health, Public Health Center have an important role, such as improving and maintaining health in the community [12].

From the results of the study, it was also found that in general, the number of patients who stated sufficient assurance was greater than the number of patients who stated less assurance. This happens because patients want the skills and knowledge of officers in providing services, friendliness, attention, and attitude of officers. Credibility associated with growing patient trust in the Public Health Center such as reputation, achievements and others. The patient's confidence in the services he receives can be seen from the knowledge and abilities of the officers, the determination of the patient's problems, the skills of the officers at work, courteous and friendly service and the guarantee of service security and trust in services.

Public Health Center are facilities that are easily accessible by all levels of society and Public Health Center are required to be responsible for providing health services and must maintain trust to increase patient satisfaction so that patients increase. Facilities are things that are intentionally provided by the Public Health Center that are used and enjoyed by patients with the aim of providing maximum comfort and satisfaction. Facilities that make it easier for patients to carry out their activities. Facilities have the existence of supporting health services [12].

In an effort to improve the quality of service, the Public Health Center itself must increase commitment and increase employee awareness and ability in serving complaints to patients, especially those who are in direct contact with patients. Consumer satisfaction is a very important thing that must be considered by the Kademangan Health Center if you want to gain the trust of the patients. Public Health Center Kademangan must be able to make patients feel satisfied with better facilities and services [12].

The results of the chi square test obtained a value of $p = 0.042$ ($p < 0.05$) meaning H_0 is rejected. This shows that there is a relationship between Assurance and Patient Satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021. This is in line with the results of research [13] which states that there is a relationship between the quality of nurse care and patient satisfaction at Balimbingan Hospital. Research [14] which says that there is a relationship between the Quality of Health Services and Visitor Satisfaction in Class III Inpatient Room Atma Husada Mahakam Regional Mental Hospital Atma Husada Samarinda. Research [15] obtained the results that the level of patient satisfaction with the quality of nurse services is very much in line with expectations. Research [16] obtained data that the dimensions of the service quality variable have the greatest influence on satisfaction. Research [17] obtained the results that of the five dimensions of service quality five dimensions have a significant effect on patient satisfaction. Research [18] found that tangibility and assurance have an effect on customer satisfaction of Sarila Husada Hospital Sragen patients. Research [19] found that there is a significant relationship between Service Quality and Satisfaction. Research [20] obtained the results of simultaneous analysis of the five variables both from physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy affect patient satisfaction. Research [21] shows that service quality has a positive effect on patient satisfaction using NHI at a Medical Rehabilitation Hospital. Research [22] shows that there is a significant positive effect of service quality on patient satisfaction in Public Health Center. This means that the higher the quality of services and health facilities provided by the Public Health Center, the higher the satisfaction of patients seeking treatment at the Public Health Center.

The quality/quality of service that has a positive value indicates that the patient's expectations have been met, so that if quality = 1 the quality is said to be good and satisfies the patient. Patient satisfaction is a level of patient feeling that arises as a result of the performance of health services obtained after the patient compares it with what he expects. Patients will feel satisfied if the performance of the health services they get is the same or exceeds their expectations and vice versa, dissatisfaction or feelings of disappointment for patients will arise if the performance of the health services they get is not in line with their expectations [24].

Customer satisfaction is a representation of service quality. The concept of this method is that service quality can be measured by comparing the expected service with service performance. Service performance itself is reflected by what consumers receive and feel. To determine the level of service quality, it can be seen whether or not there is a gap between the services received and the services expected by the patient. The greater the value of the gap between perceptions and expectations, the lower the quality of service perceived by the patient. On the other hand, the smaller the gap between perceptions and expectations, the better the service quality perceived by patients [23].

The level of satisfaction of a customer for a service that has been received can be measured by comparing each desired expectation with the quality of service it receives. If a consumer expects a service at a certain level, and what is felt is that the service received is higher than what he expected, then the consumer can be said to be very satisfied. Similarly, if the consumer expects a certain level of service, and in fact the consumer feels that the service he receives is in accordance with his expectations, then the consumer can be said to be satisfied. Conversely, if the quality of service received is lower than the expected service quality, then the consumer [23].

4. Conclusion

There is a relationship between assurance and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City with a value of $p=0.042$ ($p>0.05$). Recommendation; to increase satisfaction with health services, the Public Health Center should continue to improve the availability of service infrastructure and improve the attitude of officers in providing services.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors in the making of this scientific article have no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

All informants/respondents involved in this study have stated their consent as informants/respondents to be interviewed and provided information/information in accordance with research needs.

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